

MIT ART, DESIGN AND TECHNOLOGY UNIVERSITY
MIT School of Bioengineering Sciences & Research

7th INTERNATIONAL CONFERENCE
ON
RECENT TRENDS IN BIOENGINEERING
(ICRTB 2024)

January 19-20, 2024

ABSTRACTS

MIT School of
**Bioengineering Sciences
& Research**

Breathe Life into Engineering Career!

MIT-ADT
UNIVERSITY
PUNE, INDIA

A Leap Towards The World Class Education

PP-009

Repurposing the Dark Genome – I: Reverse Proteins

Sarangadhar Nayak and Pawan K Dhar*

Synthetic Biology Group, School of Biotechnology, Jawaharlal Nehru University, New Delhi, India

* Corresponding author: pawandhar@mail.jnu.ac.in

Abstract:In the genome's blueprint, three distinct sequence categories emerge: sequences accountable for protein encoding, RNA encoding, and sequences that play no role in expression. We asked: If evolution favoured sequences for metabolic functions, to what extent is untapped (non-expressing) and underutilized (solely RNA encoding) information accessible for continued innovation? These questions drive us to experimentally create functional proteins through the utilization of intergenic sequences from *E. coli*, as published by Dhar et al. in 2009. This ongoing study extends the scope of the original report and explores the potential of reading naturally evolved genes in reverse order to unlock novel proteins or peptides. Using the full length reverse gene data in *C.elegans*, we computationally translated 20,000 *C. elegans* protein-coding genes in reverse direction to construct a virtual library of 188 'full-length and first-in-the-class' proteins. Here, we present a brief account of these reverse proteins in terms of their sequence similarities, structural details, stability, function and cellular address. This approach opens up new opportunities of designing novel proteins and peptides towards functional outcomes. Currently the experimental studies are going on. In future, we plan to expand the search space to other model organisms and provide a public access of this new data for further experimental validation.

Keywords: Reverse coding, synthetic proteins, synthetic biology, genomics.

MIT School of Bioengineering Sciences & Research

Bioengineering is a multidisciplinary field that has gained immense importance in the global scenario. MIT School of Bioengineering Sciences & Research is a constituent unit of MIT Art, Design and Technology University that aims to prepare students for ambitious careers in bioengineering by imparting education and hands-on training through project-based learning. The school helps in introducing students to the world of untapped opportunities in biology using engineering skills. The school envisions to empower India to become a leader in Bioengineering research, development and manufacturing sectors. It offers B. Tech. (Bioengineering), Int. M. Tech. (Bioengineering), M. Tech. (Environmental Bioengineering), M.Sc (Industrial Biotechnology) and Ph.D Programs in Biotechnology, Biomedical Engineering, Bioinformatics and Biomaterials. The super-specialized courses include Pharmaceutical Engineering, Synthetic Biology, Big Data Analytics, Biosensors and IoT, Biomedical Imaging, Biomechanics, Nano-Biotechnology, Robotics, Machine Learning and Artificial Intelligence, Environmental bioengineering, etc. The school is equipped with state-of-art laboratories for carrying out high-end research and innovative product development.

Rajbaug, Next to Hadapsar, Loni Kalbhor, Pune 412201, India.

+91 744 7444 027 / 28 | +91 914 6051 841 / 42

www.mitbio.edu.in / icrtb@mituniversity.edu.in

ISBN 978-93-6039-051-8

